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INTRODUCTION

Salt marshes are coastal ecosystems of great ecological importance, playing a key role in protecting shorelines, regulating water quality, and supporting biodiversity. However, these environments are increasingly threatened by pollution, including metals from industrial, agricultural, and domestic activities. In this context, environmental restoration strategies such as phytoremediation have gained prominence for being sustainable and low-impact solutions.

OBJECTIVE

THIS STUDY AIMS TO EVALUATE THE PHYTOREMEDIATION POTENTIAL OF SALT MARSH PLANTS (SUCH AS *JUNCUS MARITIMUS*) IN THE REMOVAL OF CONTAMINANTS, INCLUDING METALS. USING AN EXPERIMENTAL APPROACH, WE SEEK TO UNDERSTAND THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THESE PLANTS IN POLLUTION REDUCTION AND THEIR IMPLICATIONS FOR THE RESTORATION OF ESTUARINE ECOSYSTEMS.

METHODOLOGY

•Revegetation:

- Plants collected from Salinas and revegetated at CMIA and Sra das Areias in Lima River estuary.
- Three replicates (R1, R2, R3) per site, each covering 1 m².
- Each replicate contained 6 transplanted samples.

•Metal analysis:

- Vegetated and non-vegetated sediment and water were collected at the three sites, and their levels were determined.

RESULTS

- Initial results show the presence of metals in sediments and water in the sites being revegetated, showing the need for their removal:

- Rhizosediments had metal concentrations equal to or higher than non-vegetated sediments.
- SAL: high levels of Zn and Cr in the water.
- ARE: higher accumulation of Mn and Fe in rhizosediments.
- CMIA: highest concentrations of Cu in rhizosediments.
- The analysis of metals from the three months is in progress.

CONCLUSION

Results will allow to investigate the feasibility of saltmarsh plants revegetation as a potential phytoremediation biotechnological solution to remove metals from estuarine environments.

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